

Enabling Seamless Interoperability of Digital Systems in Smart Cities Using API: A Systematic Literature Review

Bokolo Anthony Jnr

To cite this article: Bokolo Anthony Jnr (21 Jan 2025): Enabling Seamless Interoperability of Digital Systems in Smart Cities Using API: A Systematic Literature Review, Journal of Urban Technology, DOI: [10.1080/10630732.2024.2427543](https://doi.org/10.1080/10630732.2024.2427543)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10630732.2024.2427543>

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group

Published online: 21 Jan 2025.

Submit your article to this journal [↗](#)

View related articles [↗](#)

View Crossmark data [↗](#)

Enabling Seamless Interoperability of Digital Systems in Smart Cities Using API: A Systematic Literature Review

Bokolo Anthony Jnr

Department of Applied Data Science, Institute for Energy Technology, Os Alle 5, Halden 1777, Norway;
Department of Computer Science and Communication, Østfold University College, BRA Veien 4, 1757,
Halden, Norway

ABSTRACT

Smart cities are envisioned to achieve an urban space where systems are connected to provide value added services to citizens and stakeholders, improve quality of life, and enhance institutional effectiveness. In smart cities, digital systems are deployed that comprise a wide range of service providers who collaborate to provide digital services to citizens. Hence, there is a need for accessible data that can be used to develop innovative applications and services to improve citizens' quality of life. Unfortunately, achieving interoperability of digital systems is challenging due to isolated systems referred to as vertical silos, which cannot communicate with each other due to lack of standardization of interfaces. Thus, interoperability is seen as a barrier for the seamless transfer of data between systems deployed in smart cities. In order to facilitate interoperability of systems in smart cities, this article conducts a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) to investigate the role of Application Programming Interface (API) to enable seamless interoperability in smart cities. An SLR was employed to guide the selection of studies retrieved to adequately address the formulated research questions. Findings from this study present the importance of interoperability in smart urban environments and help in providing an overview and categorization of existing interoperability solutions to make cities smarter. The findings also identified prior interoperability approaches in smart cities. Findings present a case scenario that depicts how APIs support seamless interoperability among digital systems in a smart city environment. Lastly, the findings elaborate on available API management tools and further suggest that APIs can significantly contribute to improve interoperability between digital systems and decrease barriers in providing innovative digital services in smart cities.

KEYWORDS

urban technology;
interoperability; smart cities;
Application Programming
Interface (API) management;
digital systems; systematic
review

CONTACT Bokolo Anthony anthony.bokolo@ife.no

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group
This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The terms on which this article has been published allow the posting of the Accepted Manuscript in a repository by the author(s) or with their consent.

Introduction

Recent advances in information and communications technology (ICT) enables innovative digital services that provide citizens and stakeholders with tailored and cohesive solutions to Improve urban life. In this direction, a pioneering vision of a “smarter” city has emerged termed “smart city” (Ahlgren et al., 2016). A smart city is a sustainable urban environment where every aspect of city life is facilitated by ICT and governed in an effective way, through integrated activities addressing climate change, environmental changes, mobility, energy systems, air quality, and water (Zuccalà and Verga, 2017). Given the trend of ICT for smart sustainable urban environments, making cities smarter has been viewed to possess the potential for addressing societal issues (Noura et al., 2019). The vision of a smart city entails a municipality’s vision to deploy ICT solutions to manage a city’s resources to create a sustainable environment, and to improve economic value, and the overall quality of life (Ahlgren et al., 2016). Although, the rapid increase of urban areas has presented cities with difficulties in sustaining the quality of life of residents Anthony Jnr et al. (2021a).

Smart cities enable transformative change in urban communities to become more resilient and sustainable towards addressing increased urban populations (Anthony et al., 2019). Smart cities comprise different services including health care systems, energy distribution, public mobility, safety and others. These services need to collaborate with each other to provide effective management of urban resources and to achieve new integrated city services Anthony Jnr et al. (2020b). In order to make cities smarter, there is a need to integrate information from distributed and various systems, and huge volumes of data have to be generated, processed, shared, and used by citizens and other stakeholders (Zuccalà and Verga, 2017). However, one of the issues in smart cities is that different proprietary systems and platforms are still unable to seamlessly communicate with each other as they are not interoperable. Similarly, digital systems deployed in urban environments are faced with a lack of standardization (Zabasta et al., 2018). Besides, data are generated from different digital systems that need to be used by citizens through a common interface to improve their quality of life (Nguyen et al., 2018). Therefore, there is a need to enable horizontal data flows within these digital systems deployed in smart cities to break vendor lock-in (Brutti et al., 2019). Another issue is that these systems tend to be personalized for specific areas, so are often inflexible to communicate with external systems. For these systems to communicate seamlessly with other systems (e.g., legacy systems), and to resolve heterogeneity, interoperability is becoming progressively important (Karpenko et al., 2018).

According to IEEE, “interoperability” is the ability of two or more components or systems to exchange data and to utilize the data that has been exchanged (IEEE, 1990). It is the ability of devices to interact for a precise purpose, irrespective of their differences (Rech et al., 2018). Interoperability creates opportunities for city operators and stakeholders interested in developing innovative services, while exploiting urban data (Nesi et al., 2016). It is the capability of a system to connect with another system and to utilize the functionality of the other system. Results from prior studies (Manzaroli et al., 2010; Andročec, 2017; Anthony Jnr et al., 2019) suggested that interoperability is the most significant issue facing businesses that utilize data from diverse information systems.

Additionally, findings from the literature revealed that interoperability or incompatibility of systems is a major barrier that affects seamless data transfer between heterogeneous systems such as mobility, energy, and weather in smart cities. This is due to the lack of common protocols, standards, and interfaces that restrict data from being readily accessible and shared in a seamless approach resulting in data silos that limit various services from being discovered and developed further. Studies such as Ahlgren et al. (2016) explored how to achieve interoperability and open data produced from Internet of Things (IoT) deployed in smart cities based on a cases study. There is a need to investigate how to employ data from different sources (e.g., open data, online, real time data, and historical data), not only from IoT devices but from other platforms, deployed in smart cities to provide digital services to citizens and other stakeholders. Accordingly, there is need for an approach to support interoperability of systems in smart cities. Therefore, this study adopted a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) to explore the potential of Application Programming Interface (API) as recommended by Costin and Eastman (2019); Noura et al. (2019); Anthony Jnr et al. (2020a); Anthony Jnr et al. (2020b) for supporting cross-platform interoperability for seamless information exchanges in smart urban systems. API is suggested for enabling data access, aggregation, and service delivering to transfer data as services for citizens and stakeholders. Findings from this paper provide practitioners and researchers with the key requirements and concepts to deploy interoperable digital systems in smart cities. The structure of the article is as follows: the next section is the literature review. That is followed by a section explaining the methodology and another outlining the findings. After a discussion section, we close with our conclusions.

Literature Review

Over the years several studies have investigated issues in smart cities. But there are fewer studies that have examined how to achieve seamless interoperability of digital systems in smart cities. To the best of the author's knowledge, there are limited studies, either reviews or SLRs that were conducted explicitly on seamless interoperability in smart cities context; although a few comparative reviews and research studies exist on smart cities in general, none of them mainly focused on interoperability of digital systems as their focus was mainly on IoT and open data such as the work by Ahlgren et al. (2016). Secondly, another motivation for embarking on this important study was that interoperability and the lack of standardization are emerging research areas in smart cities. Hence, this makes interoperability in smart cities an important topic to be examined thoroughly. Respectively, a few studies that conducted reviews on interoperability in urban context include Costin and Eastman (2019) who presented a qualitative review on the need for interoperability to support seamless data exchanges in smart city systems. Interoperability has been seen as a major issue for the seamless transfer of data between heterogeneous devices deployed in smart cities. In order to enable interoperability of urban systems, the researchers conducted a holistic review of requirements, principles, and methods required to attain interoperability of smart city systems. Although this review discussed interoperability in smart cities' point of view, it is not comprehensive in its coverage on which type of interoperability.

Another review on interoperability of IoT was documented by Noura et al. (2019). The review reported on innovative solutions for enabling interoperability between

heterogenous IoT platforms and seamless information sharing between different vendors to work together. Although, contribution from the study is aimed at enabling technological interoperability of IoT platforms. Di Martino et al. (2018) carried out a study to systematically review and present reports of the most innovative architectural solutions available deployed for IoT platforms, ranging from already standardized to commercial architecture. The researchers mapped, compared, and analyzed the elements of each identified architecture to determine a unified reference to address interoperability and security. They provided solutions for improving interoperability via API mainly applicable for IoT domains. Abdelouahid et al. (2017) conducted a comparative review study on current IoT interoperability architectures according to technologies and protocols deployed as well as their strength and limitations. The architectures were compared based on flexibility, confidentiality, cost, efficiency, distributed model, and mobility. The study was mostly concerned in addressing complexity involved in different IoT devices and less concerned with data generated from different devices in cities.

Based on the fact that there are unsolved interoperability issues present in different stages, such as data, application, service, and network Andročec (2017) conducted a review to investigate service-level IoT interoperability issues and solutions. The author reviewed possible interoperability resolutions use cases and specified future research problems aligned to IoT service level interoperability. Moreover, the review is more centered on technical interoperability of IoT devices in cities. Ahlgren et al. (2016) conducted a review on interoperability and open data for IoT smart cities and identified the communication protocols for IoT devices in smart cities. The authors aimed to provide accessible open systems and open data, so that organizations and citizens can develop new applications and services. However, the research is more linked to creating open data from IoT devices and sensors in cities. Loutas et al. (2011) conducted a comparative review of existing interoperability models (ATHENA interoperability framework, IDEAS interoperability framework, LISI reference model, enterprise interoperability framework, GridWise interoperability context-setting framework, perspective on heterogeneity and types of interoperability, and future Internet enterprise systems) and based on the review the authors developed a cloud semantic interoperability model. Their approach provided significant knowledge on semantic interoperability towards addressing issues that are developed in cloud computing settings. Furthermore, findings from their review presented the identified deficiencies, gaps, needs, and issues related to semantic interoperability in a cloud environment.

This study tries to add value to the extant body of literature by covering an up-to-date synthesis of interoperability research studies in smart urban environments. Accordingly, the focus of this current study is to examine how data from different sources such as real time data, open data, and historical data can help to achieve seamless interoperability of digital systems in smart cities. Service interoperability is investigated in terms of data employed to enable seamless integrated services in smart cities to support digital services provided to citizens and stakeholders.

Methodology

An SLR is chosen as the research method to carry out this study. The SLR approach aimed to assess prior studies that are appropriate to the specific research

Figure 1. Review protocol

topic in order to present a fair assessment of an investigated topic using a rigorous and trustworthy approach (Kitchenham et al., 2009; Anthony Jnr, 2021a). SLR guidelines suggested by Kitchenham et al. (2009) were employed as the chosen research method to conduct the review. Figure 1 depicts the research review protocol adopted which comprises seven phases: research questions, search process, selection criteria for inclusion and exclusion, quality assessment criterion, document retrieval, data synthesis and extraction, and findings. The review was first conducted in December 2019 and then revised in August 2021, and finally checked in October 2023.

Research Questions

Research questions help researchers set boundaries in the conducted research area. Thus, in order to achieve the research objective of this study, five research questions were formulated to guide the research. The formulated research questions are as follows:

- RQ1: Is interoperability important in smart cities?
- RQ2: Which studies developed an interoperability method to improve smart cities?
- RQ3: What are the categories of interoperability in smart cities?
- RQ4: How can API support the interoperability of digital systems in smart cities?
- RQ5: What are the available API management tools applicable in smart cities?

RQ1 aims to explore if interoperability is important in smart cities. This inquiry aims to precisely identify if interoperability is important for making cities smarter. RQ2 mainly reviews prior studies that have been carried out similar to this current study. RQ3 is structured to explicitly identify the types of interoperability that should be addressed in smart cities. Whereas RQ4 was specifically formulated to examine how API can support interoperability of digital systems in smart cities and RQ5 aims to specify the available API management systems that can be employed in smart cities.

Search Strategy

The purpose of the search strategy is to identify studies that are relevant to the research explored (Kitchenham et al., 2009). In this study, the search strategy was employed to identify studies relevant to providing answers to the research questions. The search

strategy was conducted based on the search term and data resources to be investigated. Thus, search strings were formulated to execute online search in electronic databases by integrating keywords strings with Boolean operators (OR/AND) utilized in the search terms. The list of search keyword strings used included interoperability, smart cities, smarter cities, service interoperability, service interoperability categories, API for service interoperability, API management, smart services, digital systems, open data, real-time data, historical data, data interoperability.

In this article, the relevant studies are retrieved from well-recognized scientific databases and digital libraries selected because they are considered as appropriate libraries for SLRs in information systems. The scientific databases and digital libraries include Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science (Clarivate Analytics), ScienceDirect, ProQuest, Emerald, Taylor & Francis, Inderscience, Springer, Sage, ACM, Wiley, and IEEE Xplore. Furthermore, they provided advanced search engines with choices for conducting filtered search by keywords via publication category, year, and discipline. The search comprises various types of research publications, such as conference proceedings, journal papers, and book chapters.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria are performed to verify whether or not the retrieved studies are to be included to provide secondary data for the research questions. Accordingly, inclusion and exclusion criteria were presented based on the specified questions as seen in [Table 1](#). Hence the title and abstract of each retrieved paper were examined to ensure that the study is related to interoperability in smart cities and is able to contribute to addressing the formulated research questions. The list of inclusion and exclusion criteria for this SLR is presented in [Table 1](#).

Quality Assessment Criteria

The Quality Assessment Criteria (QAC) is considered as one of the most important stages in the selection of studies (Kitchenham et al., 2009; Anthony Jnr, 2021b), to evaluate the quality of retrieved studies. The assessment of the studies is executed based on evaluation questions (Kitchenham et al., 2009), which were framed based on the research questions and research domain being examined in the study.

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Studies published in English language	Studies that are not written in the English language
Journal articles, conference proceedings, and book chapters/books	Not journal articles, conference proceedings, or book chapters/books
Published from 1990s till date (2021)	Published before 1990s.
Studies that provide possible answers to research questions based on the title and abstract content	Remove duplicate/similar studies by retaining the most current and comprehensive version
Quantitative, qualitative, and experimental studies that provide evidence	Studies that do not provide any theoretical, empirical, or statistical evidence
Studies related to the research questions being explored	Studies not related to the research questions being explored
Studies related to SLR, interoperability, and API management in smart cities	Studies not related to SLR, interoperability, or API management in smart cities

Table 2. Quality assessment criteria

#	Questions	Response Score
1	Is the aim of the studies clearly presented?	Yes = 2, Partially = 1, No = 0
2	Is the research content well explained?	Yes = 2, Partially = 1, No = 0
3	Is the problem to be addressed stated?	Yes = 2, Partially = 1, No = 0
4	Is the developed approach well documented?	Yes = 2, Partially = 1, No = 0
5	Is any methodology explicitly stated?	Yes = 2, Partially = 1, No = 0
6	Is the data collection approach stated?	Yes = 2, Partially = 1, No = 0
7	Is the validation method well carried out?	Yes = 2, Partially = 1, No = 0

Table 2 presents the QAC questions employed in this study. Each question comprises three responses that range from yes, partially, and no. If a paper received “yes” as a response, then a score of 1 is allocated to it, a score of 0.5 is allocated to a paper that receives “partially” as response, and a score of 0 is given to a paper that receives “no” as answer. To begin the QAC process a quality number was assigned to each study and the studies were assessed based on the defined question (See Table 2). The results of the quality assessment for each selected paper were documented based on each question score and the overall scores of the paper calculated by aggregating all the individual scores of each question. Moreover, to ensure the validity and reliability of each paper, only the relevant studies that received a score higher than 3.5 are included, which is half of the total-score (7). Respectively, 60 out of 92 research studies on interoperability in smart cities were selected as the main studies. The quality assessment result for each study is presented in Table 3.

Document Retrieval

The document retrieval process is discussed in this section as seen in Figure 2 which consists of five stages. Accordingly, the first stage comprises 92 papers related to interoperability research mainly in smart cities. In the second phase, the retrieved papers were checked by carrying out duplicate checks to eliminate similar papers published retrieved from different online databases. In this phase, three papers were excluded resulting in 89 papers. In the third stage, the title and abstract were used to cross check the relevance of the remaining papers which resulted in the removal of 10 papers 79 papers remaining. Next, in the fourth phase the inclusion and exclusion criteria were employed to screen the title and abstract of each collected paper to exclude irrelevant studies, which resulted in the removal of 14 papers with 65 papers remaining. Subsequently, the 65 papers were analyzed by applying the defined QAC in the fifth stage to ensure that only quality papers were selected to provide answers to the research questions. As a result, five papers were excluded as the studies did not provide empirical evidence on how interoperability was addressed in the domain explored by the authors, making the total number of the remaining studies to be 60 selected as main studies to address the research questions examined in this research.

Data Extraction and Synthesis

This phase aims to extract evidence from the selected research papers to address the specified research questions (Kitchenham et al., 2009). In this article, the extracted and

Table 3. Results of quality assessment

Papers	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Total Score
P1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.5	5.5
P2	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	6.0
P3	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	4.0
P4	1	0	1	1	1	0.5	1	5.5
P5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	1	1	6.0
P6	1	0	0.5	1	1	0	0	3.5
P7	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.5	5.5
P8	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	5.0
P9	1	0.5	1	1	0.5	1	0	5.0
P10	1	0	1	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	4.5
P11	1	0.5	0.5	1	0	1	0	4.0
P12	1	1	1	0.5	1	0	0	4.5
P13	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	6.0
P14	1	0	1	1	1	0.5	1	5.5
P15	1	1	0	0.5	1	1	1	5.5
P16	1	0.5	1	1	0	1	1	5.5
P17	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.5	4.5
P18	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.5	4.5
P19	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	6.0
P20	1	0	1	0.5	0	1	1	4.5
P21	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	6.5
P22	1	1	0.5	1	1	0	0	4.5
P23	1	1	0	1	0.5	1	1	5.5
P24	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	4.0
P25	1	1	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	4.0
S26	1	0	1	1	0.5	1	1	5.5
P27	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	6.0
P28	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	6.0
P29	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	1	1	6.0
P30	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	6.0
P31	1	0	1	1	0.5	1	1	5.5
P32	1	0	1	1	0.5	0.5	1	5.0
P33	1	1	0	0.5	1	0.5	1	5.0
P34	1	0.5	1	1	0	1	1	5.5
P35	1	0	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	5.0
P36	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.5	5.5
P37	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	6.0
P38	1	0	1	0.5	0.5	1	1	5.0
P39	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	6.5
P40	1	1	0.5	1	1	0.5	0	5.0
P41	1	1	0	1	0.5	1	1	5.5
P42	1	0.5	1	1	1	0.5	0	5.0
P43	1	1	0	0.5	1	0	0.5	4.0
S44	1	0	1	1	0.5	1	1	5.5
P45	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	6.0
P46	1	0	1	1	0.5	1	1	5.5
P47	1	0.5	1	1	1	0.5	1	6.0
P48	1	1	0	0.5	1	1	1	5.5
P49	1	0.5	1	1	0	1	0.5	5.0
P50	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.5	4.5
P51	1	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.4	5.5
P52	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	0.5	5.0
P53	1	1	0.5	0.5	1	1	0.5	5.5
S54	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	6.5
P55	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	6.0
P56	1	0	1	1	0.5	1	1	5.5
P57	1	0.5	1	1	1	0.5	1	6.0
P58	1	1	0.5	0.5	1	1	1	6.0
P59	1	0.5	1	1	0.5	1	1	6.0
P60	1	0.5	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	5.5

Figure 2. Study selection process

synthesized data comprised descriptive evidence, such as the importance of seamless interoperability in making cities smarter along with evidence of existing interoperability approaches presented to provide answers to RQ1 and RQ2. Besides, secondary data on the categories of interoperability in smart cities were extracted to provide an answer to RQ3. Furthermore, data that were relevant to the importance of API management for seamless interoperability in smart cities were analyzed to provide answers to RQ4 by detailing the impact of API to provide access to heterogenous data produced in smart cities. Meanwhile, the answers to RQ5 report existing API management systems both commercial and open source that can be employed to improve interoperability of digital systems in smart cities.

Findings

This section presents the findings of this SLR, starting by presenting the results obtained from the SLR in line with presented research questions. Therefore, based on the identified selected research studies the findings of this review are reported based on five research questions.

Importance of Interoperability in Smart Cities

The objective of RQ1 is to examine if interoperability is important in smart cities. In smart cities several data are being generated from heterogeneous sources, the ability to connect, use, and share the data efficiently and seamlessly referred to as interoperability becomes a key challenge. According to Yliopisto (1988) interoperability in information systems domains has existed since 1988 as the ability of systems to operate in aggregation. This indicates that two systems can understand each other and use the functionality of one another. ISO/IEC referred to interoperability as the capability to transfer data, execute programs, and communicate among several functional components (Noura et al., 2019). Interoperability is the ability of systems to share specified data and operate on that data based on an open standard (Camagni et al., 2019). It implies that systems can exchange information, assess, and understand each other's information (Andročec, 2017; Anthony Jnr, 2021c).

Hence, interoperability in smart cities comprises physical devices, communication protocols, applications, services, and digital systems. that seamlessly communicate and cooperate with each other to provide value added services to citizens and stakeholders. Digital systems deployed in smart cities are based on open standards and open data, including interfaces and protocols that enable third-party integration and vendor lock-in reduction (Ahlgren et al., 2016). From the citizens' perspective interoperability is the ability of systems to mutually work with each other and utilize data produced by different systems without much effort from end-users (Legendijk and Lorentzen, 2007; Costin and Eastman, 2019). Lack of interoperability wastes time required for the provision of data that have formerly been digitalized and limit value creation due to incompatibility and loss of data (Costin and Eastman, 2019). Furthermore, smart cities are characterized by the use of different infrastructure based on standard and interoperable communication protocols where virtual and physical devices with different attributes and identities are deployed. Each of these systems possess its own proprietary protocols and standards, uses different interfaces and formats which creates closed systems usually referred to as silos or stove pipes (Noura et al., 2019).

Smart cities are no longer a futuristic idea but are gradually becoming a reality. However, before smart cities can attain their full potentials, the lack of interoperability across urban systems which comprises closed and vertically oriented systems need to be addressed (Bröring et al., 2017). These isolated systems result in interoperability problems when developers want to deploy cross-platform, and cross-domain systems, which prevent the emergence of digital ecosystems (Bröring et al., 2017; Anthony Jnr, 2021d). It also leads to limitations for businesses which aim to provide their services across different platforms, where city administrations require ICT infrastructure that supports them to remain competitive, work smarter, and respond to ever-changing citizens' needs (Manzaroli et al., 2010).

In general, smart cities are faced with several issues, where one of these challenges is non-interoperability of various systems and technologies deployed for urban development (Anthony Jnr, 2020a). Smart cities comprise different digital systems that belong to different areas such as energy, mobility, air quality, etc. which lead to vertically siloed service applications as seen in Figure 3 (Bhatt et al., 2017). The data in these digital systems is typically locked or closed and cannot be reused and shared by another system

Figure 3. Breaking down the silos barriers for creating smarter cities

or service provider. Moreover, each system employs its own types of technologies, making it not easily interoperable between other systems resulting in closed vertical platforms that produce and use data on their own (Karpenko et al., 2018). To achieve the full potential of smart cities, these deployed digital systems should be integrated as horizontally based open systems as seen in Figure 3 that exchange data to promote development of new services. Evidently, interoperability is important and relevant for smart cities as confirmed from the secondary sources in making cities smarter for sustainable development.

Prior Studies on Interoperability Methods to Make Urban Environments Smarter

Over the years, several studies have discussed the importance of interoperability in smart cities. Table 4 depicts studies that have developed different methods to enhance interoperability in urban environments.

Nonetheless, different studies were carried out to provide substantial information for researchers and practitioners to understand the role of interoperability in urban contexts. Based on the current literature, none of the above research has considered the seamless interoperability of digital systems in smart cities. Secondly, it is noticed that prior research has neglected the review of studies related to how API can enhance seamless interoperability of digital systems in smart cities grounded on concurrent data from several sources. Accordingly, this study attempts to address these shortcomings by investigating how API can be employed to enhance seamless interoperability of digital systems in making cities smarter.

Categories of Interoperability in Smart Cities

RQ3 is concerned with identifying interoperability categories that should be addressed to make cities smarter. Interoperability is an emerging area of interest in the smart city domain, due to the increased need to integrate legacy and new systems to expand the capability of cities by using the opportunity provided by innovative digital infrastructures

Table 4. Prior studies on interoperability approaches in urban environment

Authors & Contribution	Study Purpose	Interoperability Category	Technologies Deployed	Communication/ Protocol (s)	Methodology	Context
Anthony Jnr et al. (2020) employed API to improve sustainable energy generation and usage in smart cities.	Aimed to employ API to facilitate big data management for sustainable energy consumption.	Data interoperability	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) and HTTP protocol	RESTful open APIs	Literature review	Smart cities
Brutti et al. (2019) suggested a modular method to achieve interoperability.	Aimed to describe a methodology to address the challenge of cross-domain interoperability.	Cross-domain interoperability	Ontology	Open data JSON/ Extensible Markup Language (XML)	Conceptual framework	Smart cities
Costin and Eastman (2019) researched the need for interoperability to support seamless data exchanges for city systems.	Focused on reviewing the requirements and methods required to achieve smart interoperable urban systems.	System, schematic, syntactical, and semantic interoperability	Ontologies and Semantic web	Web APIs	Literature review	Smart cities
Noura et al. (2019) reviewed solutions for enabling interoperability between different platforms.	Aimed to present key challenges that prevent seamless data sharing between different IoT devices.	Device, network, syntactical, semantic, and platform interoperability.	Semantic web	RESTful open APIs	Literature review	IoT environment
Cecilio et al. (2018) developed an interoperable and integration middleware to manage smart city.	Focused to facilitate interoperability of systems in a scalable, transparent, and dynamic way.	System interoperability	HTTP, HTTPS, REST, MQTT, and Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP)	API middleware	Experiment	Smart cities
Chaturvedi and Kolbe (2018) implemented an inter-sensor service to improve interoperability over platforms.	Introduce a simple web service that helps users to connect to multiple systems and data sources.	Service interoperability	Observation service sensors	Sensor Things API	Experiments	Smart cities/ IoT environment
Fortino et al. (2018) developed a multi-layered interoperability of diverse IoT systems.	Focused to provide an interconnected and operative interoperable IoT eco-systems.	Technical, syntactical, semantic, and organizational interoperability	Wi-fi, Bluetooth, Long-Term Evolution (LTE), LoRa.	API middleware	Literature review	IoT environment

Karpenko et al. (2018) investigated data exchange for interoperability for smart electric vehicle charging and parking.	Focused on describing the practical use of open standards for realizing interoperability for smart mobility.	Communication (technology and interface) and data (syntactic and semantic) interoperability.	Open Messaging Interface (O-MI) and Open Data Format (O-DF) protocols	APIs via Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP)	Experiment	Smart cities/ IoT environment
Nguyen et al. (2018) deployed Olliot-Open City to support open standard and platform interoperability	Aimed to offer data discovery to address distributed services in different repositories.	Data interoperability	Machine-to-Machine (M2M) and FIWARE.	XML/JSON, REST/SOAP using APIs via HTTP.	Case study	Smart cities
Pradhan et al. (2018) proposed data model and architecture to support interoperability between linked mission networks and systems.	Aimed to improve interoperability between systems and networks allowing multiple users to exchange and share data.	Data interoperability	LTE, LoRaWAN, and Wi-Fi.	XML/JSON, REST/SOAP using HTTP, MQTT using Secure Sockets Layer (SSL).	Conceptual framework	Smart cities/ IoT environment
Rech et al. (2018) suggested how to enhance interoperability between different applications.	Aimed to find common interfaces for connecting the underlying industries with each other.	Business interoperability	Tokenization (distributed Kerberos based authentication procedure).	RESTful API	Conceptual framework	Smart cities
Zabasta et al. (2018) deployed MQTT protocol to support interoperability of urban systems.	Aimed to resolve systems incompatibility and improve technical integration.	Device interoperability	MQTT protocol	Data flow programming tool Node-RED and APIs for online services	Case study	Smart cities/ IoT environment
Androćec (2017) researched how to address service interoperability issues in the IoT domain.	Focuses on reviewing use case of service-category IoT interoperability issues and solutions.	IoT interoperability	Semantic web and ontology	Cloud REST APIs	Literature review	IoT environment
Bröring et al. (2017) supports IoT eco-systems via platform interoperability.	Focused to bridge the interoperability gap of devices and ignite the city ecosystem.	Platform interoperability	Semantic web	BIG IoT API	Conceptual framework	IoT environment
Robert et al. (2017) suggested an open IoT ecosystem for increased interoperability.	Aimed to enhance system interoperability and improve service co-creation.	Device interoperability	Semantic web	LoRa and RESTful APIs	Experiment	Smart cities/ IoT environment

(Continued)

Table 4. Continued.

Authors & Contribution	Study Purpose	Interoperability Category(s)	Technologies Deployed	Communication/ Protocol (s)	Methodology	Context
Ahlgren et al. (2016) explored how IoT facilitates smart cities in addressing open data and interoperability.	Aimed to provide open systems and open data for citizens and enterprises to develop new applications and services.	Open interoperability	MQTT protocol	Open data and open APIs	Case study	Smart cities/ IoT environment
Gyvard and Serrano (2016) presented an approach to improve interoperability and connection of things.	Aimed to reduce gap and provide a standard format of the data among IoT systems.	Technical, syntactical, semantic, and organizational interoperability	Semantic web	Linked open data	Use case application	Smart cities/ IoT environment
Kovacs et al. (2016) presented a standard world-wide semantic approach to improve IoT interoperability.	Focused on presenting a system architecture for realizing world-wide interoperable standards.	Semantic interoperability	Machine-to-Machine (M2M) and FIWARE.	REST-API via HTTP, CoAP, and MQTT	Experiment	IoT environment
Desai et al. (2015) developed an architecture based on semantic gateway as a service to improve IoT interoperability.	Aimed to provide a gateway to improve interoperability between platforms using different standards.	System interoperability	W3Cs Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) ontology, RDF, XML, and JSON.	CoAP, MQTT, Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol (XMPP), and REST.	Conceptual framework	IoT environment
Bedogni et al. (2013) proposed an interoperable architecture for mobile services via the Internet of energy.	Aimed to facilitate the implementation of smart mobile services for electric mobility scenario.	Information interoperability	RDF ontology	APIs expose RDF for XML transported over TCP.	Omnet++ Simulation	IoT environment
Manzaroli et al. (2010) designed an interoperability system to provide a simple and generic solution to develop smart applications.	Intended to improve information interoperability within service level interoperability.	Information interoperability	Semantic web	Zigbee and Wi-Fi Bundle	Literature review	Smart environment
Berre et al. (2007) developed the ATHENA interoperability framework for enterprise systems and applications.	Aimed to provides a reference approach for addressing interoperability problems	System interoperability	Semantic web	Model-driven XML	Literature review	Smart cities

Figure 4. Levels of interoperability in smart cities adapted from Costin and Eastman (2019)

(Karpenko et al., 2018). But smart cities services are faced with interoperability barriers such as different operating systems, programs written in different or non-compatible computer languages, enterprises wanting to keep their software proprietary, or companies using different data formats and schemas (Costin and Eastman, 2019). Additionally, digital systems in smart cities need to be interoperable to realize seamless application integration across service boundaries and beyond. Hence, the transfer of data among different platforms requires systems to be interoperable with each other (Anthony Jnr et al., 2019).

Accordingly, Figure 4 depicts the levels of service interoperability in smart cities as derived from Table 4 (in the interoperability categories column). Figure 4 shows the levels of interoperability in smart cities that comprise physical, data, and communication interoperability. Accordingly, data from devices needs communication interoperability, after which the data is processed and integrated for data interoperability to be utilized by different organizations and stakeholders for enterprise interoperability to be utilized for providing services for citizens via physical interoperability.

Figure 5 depicts the categories of interoperability and their associated sub clusters in smart cities. Each of the categories is discussed below.

Communication Interoperability. Communication interoperable systems can be seen as two or more individuals from several nations speaking their own language to each other, where information is received but not understood (Berre et al., 2007). Communication interoperability provides mechanisms, infrastructures, and paths for data exchange between two or more different networks, IT solutions, applications, or organizations. Communication interoperability comprises technological and interface interoperability (Karpenko et al., 2018).

- **Interface Interoperability.** Interface level interoperability provides the required communication interface which allows different systems to communicate among each

Figure 5. Clusters of interoperability in smart cities

other and exchange data whenever required, irrespective of who needs the data. These communication interfaces need to be generic, and able to support data exchange requirements and openness for digital systems deployed in smart cities (Karpenko et al., 2018).

- *Technology Interoperability.* Technology interoperability forms the basis of data exchange interoperability, which supports two or more entities or systems to communicate with each other. Technology interoperability can be attained by deploying a common agreed data transmission medium and guidelines of data access (Desai et al., 2015). Basically, it deploys a physical communication channel with a low-level protocol structure. Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol (TCP/IP) which is one of the most accepted solutions can be deployed to achieve technology interoperability (Karpenko et al., 2018).

Data Interoperability. While communication interoperability supports data exchange between two or more different systems, it does not specify the structure and format of the data that has been exchanged (Fortino et al., 2018; Karpenko et al., 2018). However, data interoperability is concerned with the semantics and structure of data that make different systems interoperable (Karpenko et al., 2018). Data interoperability comprises syntactic and semantics interoperability.

- *Syntactic Interoperability.* Syntactic interoperability refers to the structure and format of data that have been exchanged between different systems (Andročec, 2017; Bröring et al., 2017). The syntactic aspect refers to describing the exact format of the information to be exchanged in terms of grammar and format (EC-European Commission, 2017). Thus, syntactic interoperability involves machine readable features of data representation. In order to attain syntactic interoperability in smart urban systems, data exchanged between platforms that are interoperable at communication interoperability should have a well-defined structure, encoding, and syntax for the data that are being exchanged (Fortino et al., 2018; Noura et al., 2019). Hence, data formats should be general enough to be able to characterize any data that will be exchanged, thus enabling heterogeneous platforms to understand the format or structure of data, although syntactic interoperability does not support the involved stakeholders to understand the meaning of exchanged information (Costin and Eastman, 2019; Anthony Jnr, 2020b).

In smart cities context, syntactic interoperability involves describing the main format of the data to be exchanged in terms of format such as JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) or Extensible Markup Language (XML) and grammar (EC-European Commission, 2017). Syntactical interoperability involves reusing and combining different datasets developed with diverse platforms dealing with different syntaxes e.g., Resource Description Framework (RDF)/XML, Notation3 (N3) (Gyrard and Serrano, 2016). Additionally, syntactic interoperability can be realized through clearly defined and specified interface and data formats as well as encodings (Bröring et al., 2017), aims at enhancing systems component cooperation with diverse development platforms and implementation languages (Andročec, 2017).

- *Semantic Interoperability.* Semantic interoperability is associated with the meaning of data content and is more concerned with human rather than machine interpretation of the data content (Fortino et al., 2018). Thus, semantic interoperability relates to the meaning of data (Andročec, 2017). Semantic interoperability aims to confirm that the meaning of exchanged information is understood by the communicating parties, with the purpose of value creation in other words what is sent is what is understood (Costin and Eastman, 2019; Anthony Jnr et al., 2020a). Semantic interoperability requires that devices in smart cities speak the same language and can be accomplished by deploying agreed upon data models (Andročec, 2017; Bröring et al., 2017). Additionally, semantic interoperability ensures that the correct meaning and format of exchanged data is understood and well-maintained throughout the exchanges between communicating parties involved (Noura et al., 2019). In smart urban environments, semantic

interoperability refers to the meaning of data elements and the relationship among them. It comprises developing schema and vocabularies to describe data exchanges (EC-European Commission, 2017).

Physical Interoperability. Physical interoperability requires that hardware such as IoT devices, sensors, metering devices, etc., can speak and be heard (Andročec, 2017). This is because hardware forms the main components required to run digital systems used in smart cities as this hardware produces data (Costin and Eastman, 2019), that can be utilized to provide value added services to citizens but are faced with interoperability challenges which comprise technical, device, network, and platform interoperability.

- *Technical Interoperability.* Smart cities are supported by legacy systems that are connected to isolated digital systems that are difficult to connect and share data. Hence the isolated plethora of legacy systems creates additional interoperability barriers that need to be addressed. Thus, technical interoperability aids the use of formal technical specifications (EC-European Commission, 2017). It comprises the infrastructures and applications linking data services and systems. It enables machine-to-machine communication among hardware devices (Gyrard and Serrano, 2016). Additionally, in smart cities, technical interoperability consists of interconnection services, data presentation and exchange interface specifications, data integration services, and secure communication protocols (EC-European Commission, 2017). According to Fortino et al. (2018) technical interoperability is linked to communication protocols and the infrastructure required for those protocols to be deployed in smart cities (Fortino et al., 2018).
- *Device Interoperability.* Currently when devices want to exchange information, they use different communication technologies that necessitate interoperability between heterogeneous devices that co-exist in digital systems utilized in smart cities (Noura et al., 2019). Accordingly, device interoperability facilitates the integration of heterogeneous devices broadcasting with different communication standards and protocols supported by heterogeneous IoT devices. Device interoperability aims to provide communication media due to the lack of de facto communication standard(s) that prevent smart devices from using similar communication technologies. Thus, it is concerned with exchange of information between different devices and communication protocols, and it is the ability to integrate new devices into a city's ecosystems (Noura et al., 2019).
- *Network Interoperability.* Smart cities operate on networks that comprise devices which continue to be multi-vendor, and as such heterogeneous, largely distributed, and multi-service. Respectively, network interoperability deals with mechanisms to support seamless message/information exchange between systems through diverse networks (networks of networks) for end-to-end communication (Noura et al., 2019). To make such systems interoperable, each system must be able to exchange information with other systems over different types of networks. Due to the dynamic and heterogeneous network environment in smart cities, network interoperability handles challenges such as Quality of Service (QoS), mobility support, security, routing, and resource optimization (Noura et al., 2019).

- *Platform Interoperability.* The platform interoperability challenge in smart cities arises due to the use of different operating systems, data structures, programming languages, data access mechanisms, and architectures for devices and data (Andročec, 2017; Noura et al., 2019). Presently, there are different operating systems developed and utilized by devices, each with different versions deployed to provide services to citizens. Besides, several vendors in smart cities use cross-platform and cross-domain applications. Hence, stakeholders and developers that provide services to citizens need extensive knowledge of data models of each platform to be able to adapt their applications from one platform to another (Costin and Eastman, 2019; Noura et al., 2019).

As seen in this section there is a lack of studies that have explored service interoperability in smart cities. Accordingly, a cross-platform application such as API is needed to integrate data from various platforms enabling seamless interoperability across digital systems enabling data collection from heterogeneous domains federated to build horizontal smart applications for integrated services for mobility, energy, etc. (Noura et al., 2019). Therefore, this study is more aligned with achieving service interoperability based on API deployed to provide access to open data, real-time data, and historical data as discussed in the next sub-section.

Application of API to Support Service Interoperability in Smart Urban Environments

With respect to the fourth research question, this section is dedicated to discussing how API can enhance service interoperability in smart cities. Accordingly, discussion on open data, the role of API, and RESTful API is presented below as these help to achieve seamless interoperability of digital systems towards the provision of value-added services to citizens and stakeholders in smart cities.

Open Data for Service Interoperability in Smart Urban Environments. Interoperability in smart cities aims to link existing systems to provide open data to stakeholders (citizens, communities, businesses) within the city, opening up potentials for innovation (Brutti et al., 2019). According to Barbosa et al. (2016) “open data” is data that the original source can be freely used, redistributed, and reused by anyone under the same licenses in which the data was originally shared. Moreover, open data refers to data which can be freely used by anyone. The European Union (EU) has been advocating for open data initiatives with the aim of increasing transparency, properly capacitating citizens, fostering innovations and improving public services (EC-European Commission, 2017).

Additionally, the use of open data in smart cities aims to provide data freely available to foster citizen empowerment, improve public services through involvement, leveraging innovative business models, and eventually changing the approach on which city administrations operate (Barbosa et al., 2016). However, most data in smart cities are still locked away in incompatible formats with various semantics that prevent open data to be used by stakeholders (Brutti et al., 2019). Thus, open data is certainly an imperative enabler of urban “smartification” contributing to innovation in providing digital services to citizens and enterprises operating within the city.

API for Service Interoperability in Smart Urban Environment. In smart cities data are produced from building management systems, traffic and mobility systems, water and pollution management, energy grids, social media, e-governance systems, and many more. These heterogeneous data represents a vital basis for planning and decision processes in making cities smarter. Thus, there is need to highlight the importance of opening up and providing access to these data to citizens and stakeholders to encourage and support novel application services. To enable these services as well to promote open data exchange, it is vital to provide a medium to access and expose data in predictable, secure, and efficient ways to produce value added services to citizens (Schleicher et al., 2017). Currently in the literature, there are prior studies (Barbosa et al., 2016; Bhatt et al., 2017; Rech et al., 2018), that proposed middleware approaches to provide abstractions towards developing smart city applications. However, they do not fully address seamless interoperability needed to manage and make cities smarter (Ahlgren et al., 2016).

A city can only become smarter if it is an intelligent city where different infrastructures are able to communicate and share data with each other and function as an ecosystem through middleware that serves as connectors (Anthony Jnr et al., 2019). Accordingly, middleware is a software program that enables interoperability across diverse devices and abstract the functionalities of each device (Brundu et al., 2016). In this context, to make a city smarter, a generic middleware platform such as API is required (Cecilio et al., 2018). Respectively, API is suggested as recommended by Dhungana et al. (2015); Noura et al. (2019) to address the aforementioned issues related to data silos in addressing seamless interoperability of digital systems. APIs support application-to-application communication by having the subroutine definitions and protocols, functions, and systems accessible to use (Costin and Eastman, 2019). API was developed and patented in 1996 by Frank Bergler who referred to API as a middleware for combined digital services such that system applications can be produced autonomously (Choi et al., 2013). API allows diverse data to be utilized seamlessly to share data and services in a homogenous scenario. API enables smart city applications to automatically connect and discover the right information sources, that facilitates seamless use (Anthony Jnr et al., 2019).

Additionally, API can be referred to as a gateway deployed by service providers to expose data or functions to an application coded in a high-level language. APIs usually utilizes Representational State Transfer (REST) principles which allow operations such as PUT, GET, PUSH, or DELETE (Anthony Jnr et al., 2019). APIs are developed to decrease the complexity faced in deploying applications as well as seamless interoperability issues associated with massive development of smart city platform providers that generate vast silos of heterogeneous data (Noura et al., 2019). An API provides access to open data for third parties to use city data generated by smart devices and platforms to drive development of innovative application services (Ahlgren et al., 2016). Moreover, an API aims to aggregate processed data from a wide variety of smart devices and sensors to support cross-city federation between different enterprises, users, platforms, and seamlessly present information to citizens and stakeholders to support decisions in terms of resource reduction planning and investment (Borgogno and Colangelo, 2019).

Furthermore, the data provided via APIs also support the creation of a new set of digital services that can help citizens and city managers make beneficial and better

choices around smart services such as energy, air quality and mobility, which when scaled up will improve a city's ability to achieve key targets for transportation, energy efficiency and resilience, economic development, etc. (Holley et al., 2014). Additionally, APIs provide a scalable governance mechanism of digital systems (Borgogno and Colangelo, 2019). More recently, the European Commission has begun to investigate a possible future EU framework for data access that offers an environment which promotes aggregation, sharing, and reuse of machine-generated data that could be used to create new business models (Borgogno and Colangelo, 2019).

APIs are different from standard web services in their emphasis on simplicity, meeting the requirements of modern application developers, and leveraging web protocols such as Hyper Text Transfer Protocol (HTTP), REST, and JSON for scalability (Holley et al., 2014). Hence, smart city services and data are no longer locked inside applications which lead to loss of data and application silos. Likewise, APIs deploy RESTful web service which aids city developers and businesses to easily implement their web service via HTTP protocol (Choi et al., 2013), which allow IoT devices in smart cities environment to speak the same language thus make data resources easy and accessible (McGrath et al., 2019).

Applicability of RESTful API for Service Interoperability. Representational State Transfer (REST) is the most common protocol employed for deploying application services (Anthony Jnr et al., 2019). REST was designed by “Roy Fielding” in his doctoral thesis as an approach for implementing multi-distributed systems based on client server architecture (Fielding and Taylor, 2000; Holley et al., 2014). Although few cities provide their services by deploying traditional Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP) web service other than RESTful web-based services. But SOAP web service is criticized due to its complicated features as compared to REST web service which eliminates the overhead via encoding/decoding of message header and body during data transfer (Anthony Jnr et al., 2019). Moreover, REST web service facilitates users and developers to simply use the web services at local or remote sites. REST protocol does not include additional communication layers for data service (Choi et al., 2013), hence REST can easily achieve performance and scalability, thus suitable for intelligent application development in smart cities. This is because the REST web service deploys HTTP which is appropriate for accessing information across the Internet (Choi et al., 2013).

REST protocol exposes web services and access to data either raw or post-processed exploiting open data to enhance development of innovative services. In this view, REST protocol enhances easy-to-use interfaces that comprise individual components which are easy to use and manage for developing distributed smart applications (Brundu et al., 2016), creating a shared data environment in smart cities for extensive service interoperability. Over the decades, REST APIs has emerged as an important element that supports dynamic provision of data from different data sources in response to clients' command (Raetzsch et al., 2019). Additionally, organizations such as Google, Yahoo, and Amazon now provide REST APIs for providing access to their digital services to end users. REST is becoming explosively popular and is used for developing applications for web and smartphone (Brundu et al., 2016).

A typical procedure for service interoperability in smart cities via REST API for energy data in a city comprises a metering device connecting to a database and citizens who

retrieve saved energy data to make decisions on electricity usage. The first step involves connecting physical devices such as metering devices and energy sensors to a non-relational database such as Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) to collect generated real-time energy data to be stored. The connection below shows an example for JSON format of energy metering device employed to measure real-time streaming of energy data in a building based on HTTP POST request is presented below.

```
Request URL : http://localhost:8080/energy\_consumption-rest/HDFS
Method : POST
Content Type: application/json
{
  "name": "energy_metering_device_stream",
  "description": "Live consumption energy metering device",
  "connectionType": "web socket",
  "measurementType": "binary",
  "unitOfCalibration": "Percent",
  "serviceName": "EnergyConsumptionAPI",
  "serviceType": "JSON",
  "baseUrl": "http://municipality.consumption-energy-metering.no/v1.2",
  "deviceId": "00012",
  "datastreamId": "123354",
  "observationParameter": "Energy"
}
```

The energy metering device can be connected to the HDFS to disseminate generated energy data using a HTTP POST request by employing REST protocol streaming at port 8080. This can help to achieve interoperability towards enhancing urban smartness in providing data to energy consumers in smart cities via a digital platform to improve energy consumption as well as energy produced. Furthermore, citizens can use HTTP GET query based on the EnergyConsumption REST API service instantiates to invoke simple query to retrieve energy consumption measurement towards enhancing city smartness using HTTP GET requests as shown in the JSON format below.

```
GET Request: http://localhost:8080/energy\_consumption-rest/HDFS
{
  "id": "002",
  "HDFSdataSourceConnection":
  {
    "name": "energy_metering_device_stream",
    "description": "Live consumption energy metering device",
    {"timestamp": "2021-07-25T20:29:15 PM",
    "assignedvalue": 20.0}
    {"time": "2021-07-25T21:00:00 PM ",
    "value": 43.2
  }}
  {}
  {"id": "007,
```

```

"name": " energy_metering_device _stream ",
"description": " Live consumption energy metering device ",
"connectionType": "web socket",
"firstMeasurement": "2021-07-25T20:29:15 PM",
"lastMeasurement": "2021-07-25T21:00:00 PM",
"observationParameter": "Energy",
"MeasurementType": "binary",
"unitOfCalibration": "Percent"
}

```

The JSON example presented above depicts how REST “GET” request is employed for retrieving time-varying observations belonging to a specific time series within a specific time range for enhancing city smartness. This is based on two data parameters time series and data sources (real time data and historical data), employed to retrieve static information about energy consumption based on measured parameter which is “live consumption energy metering device” and different time series belonging to a collected energy data saved in HDFS repository. Thus, REST API is recommended and encoded in either XML or JSON as energy data output formats as suggested by McGrath et al. (2019) because both formats are easy to produce and parse, structured, lightweight documents and are machine readable. Also, GET request structure comprises the resource location that is being retrieved, the output format, and the consumption energy parameters, structured by “&” (Chaturvedi and Kolbe, 2018; McGrath et al., 2019).

Currently, only a few studies have explored the applicability of REST web service protocol in smart cities. Thus, the research area of REST API is underexplored and studies in this domain are still in their infancy. Thus, this article recommends RESTful web service since it offers the most convenient way for accessing data through the Internet. Consequently, RESTful APIs are proposed to extend smart service business capabilities via application deployed to support in enhancing urban smartness towards enabling cities get smarter. RESTful APIs are directly called from the browser or within digital platforms used by citizens and stakeholders (for instance, Hypertext Markup Language [HTML]) and directly retrieve information from database emancipating interoperable seamless data from siloed, data sources, accessing information locked inside external and internal data sources to help in improving smart cities sustainability goals.

Case Scenario for Service Interoperability in Smart Cities. An architecture is presented to depict how APIs are employed to support service interoperability in smart cities. Grounded on prior study (Anthony Jnr et al., 2021a) where an architecture was presented as seen in [Figure 6](#).

The architecture comprises different layers as seen in [Figure 6](#). A case scenario for seamless interoperability of digital systems in smart cities is shown in [Figure 7](#) modeled in ArchiMate modeling language. As seen in [Figure 7](#) the context layer comprises the set of goals, constraints, principles, and main requirements related to digital service in smart cities. The context layer also captures the interests of stakeholders and citizens such as seamless digital experience and increase update of digital solutions as illustrated in [Figure 7](#). The service layer is responsible for presenting the city’s action

Figure 6. Proposed architecture adapted from Anthony Jnr et al., 2021b

plans, resources, and capabilities. The service layer also provides interfaces which deliver digital services to citizens. Thus, the service layer aims to effectively implement specified outputs and competently realizing specified key performance goals within the city such as service booking and making payment for different mobility services within a single application as seen in [Figure 7](#).

The business layer is responsible for listing all enterprises involved in providing digital services to stakeholders. Thus, the business layer involves virtual enterprises that cooperate in providing digital services to citizens to support making city services smarter. The application and data processing layer encompass all systems deployed to provide digital services to stakeholders. Moreover, the application and data processing layer process and transform data into useful information to provide digital services and insights. Hence, it provides applications and APIs that expose digital services to support the actualization of seamless digital services to improve seamless service interoperability as seen in [Figure 7](#).

The data space layer specifies which data are being used by the enterprises in providing digital services within the city. The data space layer consists of real-time data, online data, historical data, and third-party data from external sources. The data space layer provides access to data sources through APIs as seen in [Figure 7](#). The technological layer comprises all the technologies deployed across the city such as ubiquitous computing, big data, processing, cloud computing, service-oriented architecture, etc. The technology layer provides the required software and hardware infrastructures needed to provide digital services in smart cities. This layer consists of infrastructures needed to collect, process, handle, and store urban data.

The physical infrastructures comprise physical assets within the city that generate data. The physical infrastructures layer produces real-time data generated from physical sources that are transferred to the technology layer. This layer comprises physical infrastructures such as sensors, metering devices, IoT devices, sensing devices deployed within the city that generate data. As seen in the case scenario the physical infrastructures

Figure 7. Case scenario for seamless interoperability of digital systems in a smart city environment

comprise public transport means used within a city for mobility. Also, Figure 6 comprises the data perspectives and stakeholders’ perspectives. Stakeholders’ perspectives include policies and regulations, data ownership and access, and privacy and trust. Whereas the data perspective comprises data standards, data interoperability, risk assessment, security, and data governance (Anthony Jnr et al., 2021b).

Existing API Management Tools Applicable in Smart Urban Environment

Importance of API Management Systems. As APIs become pervasive, the complexity of maintaining APIs has increased, thus in smart cities there is need for API management (Anthony et al., 2020). Respectively, API management involves the procedure involved in

creating and publishing web APIs applying usage policies, regulatory access, maintaining subscriber clients, collecting, and analyzing usage data, and monitoring performance. API management provides methods to support developer and user's community in maintaining the lifecycle of APIs (Kerner, 2019).

API management provides consistent documentation, increased security, thorough testing, consistent versioning, high maintenance, etc. API management systems or tools support city developers with the earliest phases of smart service API planning, design, and development, and testing which helps to make sure that APIs are compatible in different platforms. Finally, once an API has been developed and tested, it is published and deployed, then the API lifecycle management commences from operations to consumption, as well as security and versioning (softwaretestinghelp.com, 2019). A typical API management system provides gateway, publishing tools, developer portal or API store, reporting and analytics, monetization, opensource, and facilitates governance as seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8 depicts the functions of API management system each of which are discussed below:

- **Provides gateway:** refers to a front-end API server that enforces throttling policies, receives API requests, and sets security rules, re-directs requests to the back-end

Figure 8. Functions of API management system

server which provides response back to clients. A gateway often comprises a conversion engine that modifies and orchestrates requests and responses. It also supports collection of data analytics, implements authorization regulatory compliance, authentication, security, and audit.

- **Publishing tools:** this comprises tools that API providers employ to describe APIs for example using the Open API specifications. These tools can be used to generate API documentation, manage usage policies and access for APIs, debug and test the execution of API, including deploying APIs into staging, production, and quality assurance, and organizing the complete API lifecycle.
- **Developer portal or API store:** entails a community site that comprises a single secured administrator profile for city developers to manage source code functionality, software development kits and information including documentation and an interactive API sandbox and console to manage API subscription licenses.
- **Reporting and analytics:** this supports monitoring of API consumption. This can consist of real-time monitoring of API log usage with alert notifications. The information produced can be utilized to optimize API services for continuous improvements for citizens who use the service.
- **Monetization:** relates to the API management system providing options for deploying commercializing API for financial benefits. This may include setting up pricing policies, based on service functionality usage and integrating the payment gateway for generating invoices after processing payments.
- **Open source:** relates to API management systems that can be deployed by cities without license or payment subscription.
- **Facilitate governance:** involves API management systems that support the stipulating rules and regulation toward API usage.

Based on these aforementioned functions a few API management tools provide these functionalities to enable city developers to manage and share their APIs to be used to develop digital platforms to support services such as smart mobility, health, etc.

Existing API Management Systems Applicable in Smart Cities

This section aims to review existing API management tools that can be deployed to orchestrate seamless interoperability in making cities smarter. Accordingly, the identified API management system comprises Apigee, 3scale, IBM API Management, Akana, Kong Enterprise, Dell Boomi, Mashery, Automate, MuleSoft, Microsoft Azure, Oracle API manager, Postman, Axway, WSO2, and Cloud Elements as shown in [Table 5](#).

Based on the review of available API management tools (See [Tables 5 and 6](#)). In [Table 6](#) “y” = yes “meaning the software does support” and “n” = no “meaning the software does not support”. As seen in [Table 6](#) Apigee is the best in monetizing APIs, whereas 3scale is a suitable choice based on its developer portal. Akana provides the most effective API lifecycle management system, whereas 3scale, Kong, and WSO2 are open-source free API management tools. Additionally, Dell Boomi is more suitable for integrating cloud-based services and Mashery is more aligned for supporting conversion among SOAP and RESTful protocols. MuleSoft is suitable for cities wanting to connecting services in achieving an interoperable eco-system of seamless applications. Automate

Table 5. API management systems applicable in smart cities

API Systems	Description
Apigee	Apigee is considered a top API management vendor and is suitable for small and medium-sized cities to provide powerful service analytics that provides metrics information on API traffic usage and is best known for measuring Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and supporting API monetization. Apigee API provides operations analytics, security, monitoring, monetization, and city developer portal. It also offers API solutions as an agent or proxy, enabling city developers to deploy smart applications in urban environments.
3scale	3scale was developed by Red Hat Software to help control, share, distribute, monetize, and secure APIs. It provides API tools for access control, dashboard analytics, usage traffic control, rate limits, etc. 3scale is open source and provides the best developer portal. 3scale is currently a good choice for developing cities as well as medium or large municipalities such as smart cities. Besides, it also supports API monetization and can be deployed on the cloud or on site.
IBM API Tool	IBM supports API creation and management through a cloud-based solution which provides in-house governance and security functionalities. It offers a developer portal platform for simple coding, and real-time usage analytics that can be available to API providers as well as users. IBM API supports traffic metrics on API usage, monitoring and testing without coding. Moreover, it supports city developers to get the most out of their API usage and optimize revenue/monetize APIs. But it is more suitable for medium to large sized cities. IBM's API tool provides a user-friendly platform that connects to backend data sources to create and manage APIs.
Akana	Akana provides an end-to-end API management system that facilitates the design, implementation, publishing, securing, and monitoring of APIs. It offers a developer portal from which it can be deployed locally or via the cloud. Besides, Akana deploys RESTful API that supports usage traffic management, detects security vulnerabilities during API run-time and is more suitable for API lifecycle management mainly for medium to large-scaled cities.
Kong API Tool	Kong is an easy open-source tool that is available for free and can be deployed locally or in the cloud, or as a hybrid. The functionality of Kong can be extended via plugins that enable city developers to extend the built-in functionalities and also improve scalability and is well suited for any size of cities providing API gateway capabilities. It supports commercial capabilities that help cities for API automation and usage visualization via a built-in developer portal that provides API catalog.
Dell Boomi	Dell Boomi provides a solution that helps connect data and applications across the cloud and can also be deployed in a hybrid environment. It utilizes a library of connectors that link various cloud-based applications supporting integration. Dell Boomi helps with data and application integration capabilities enabling organizations to design and publish APIs with a well thought out workflow to expose data and services to clients.
Mashery	Mashery provides a cloud solution to manage the full life cycle of developed API. It supports API developers to carryout API creation, packaging, testing, and management. It also provides locally, or cloud based configured API gateway for better security and offers a developer portal for API analytics. Mashery is deployed as RESTful and SOAP protocol conversion. It also supports the monetization of deployed APIs so they can easily be consumed by city developers and partners.
Automate	Automate is developed by CA Technologies to provide a cloud centric solution for API management. It provides an agile low code development system for API development in maintaining micro services and is more suitable to manage the development of IoT-based mobile services. It offers a developer portal and is best for providing an API gateway for seamless data integration across different platforms. Using Automate API tool cities can virtualize API productivity improvements to facilitate cities seeking to deploy APIs to develop powerful applications and open economic opportunities.
MuleSoft	MuleSoft provides a solution for developing API locally, on the cloud. It aids in the design and management of APIs on heterogeneous platforms. It offers a developer portal that secures APIs via policies, manages users, analyzes usage traffic. It provides an API gateway that provides central visibility and control of deployed API and is best known for building and connecting APIs, offering a robust tool for API creation, execution and management, with a usable interface to manage continuous integration of cities in eliminating siloed operations. Additionally, it provides a set of security measures such as API tokenizing, data, and edge gateway policies.
Microsoft Azure	Microsoft Azure API management tool enables city developers to manage all APIs in one place. It employs Internet Protocol (IP) filtering, token and key security functionalities for APIs. It also provides insights via API analytics and provides access to publish APIs for internal and external clients. Further, it supports API gateways creation, publishing and management of microservices, access to a developer portal and is best known for offering a self-service API key management platform on the web. Additionally, it offers a user-friendly system for cities of any size in managing APIs based on a self-service method. Its API management includes consumption tracking and version control is integrated with the Azure cloud making it easy for cities to use Microsoft's cloud services.

(Continued)

Table 5. Continued.

API Systems	Description
Oracle API Manager	Oracle API manager supports the creation of APIs as REST and SOAP. It helps to monitor and track API's performance and enables the transformation of complex service integrations into reusable and agile service-based applications for shorter time and lower costs. It offers an Oracle process manager that governs and provides a complete easy-to-use solution for assembling disconnected services into an integrated service.
Postman	Postman provides a comprehensive development environment for the design, deployment, debug, and monitoring of APIs in creating a group of API endpoints. It provides integrated solutions for each phase of the API lifecycle and supports teams to collaborate in setting permissions, managing involvement, and sharing roles in collaborative workspaces. Postman is a suitable choice for cities' that are mostly concerned with API development as their main focus. Postman employs an API development environment with integrated tools to aid city developers create, test, and deploy APIs.
Axway	Axway provides a cloud data integration system that securely connects devices, apps, and systems. It offers API management tools needed by city developers to create, publish, manage, and document APIs in a secure deployment environment. Axway also helps to manage connections between APIs and applications in extending digital services with unique business agility. Additionally, it provides a complete API lifecycle management integration solution via a developer portal which allows for logging real-time API analytics to help cities react quickly and innovate new services to citizens and stakeholders.
WSO2	WSO2 provides an open-source system for API management. It has functionalities that support the complete API lifecycle management, policy enforcement, and monetization. WSO2 is best known for providing customizability and freely open source. WSO2 deploys an API manager which is available locally which can be hosted on a public API cloud version. It also supports identity management for application security and analytics capabilities that provide API usage metrics and monetization options for deployed APIs. WSO2 is more suitable for technologically oriented cities that are interested in deploying fully open-source systems for API management. WSO2 also supports microservices via a micro-gateway which aids to accomplish API policy management in a decentralized approach.
Cloud Elements	Cloud elements offer an API integration system for digital services and cloud providers to connect disparate services and data sources via elements and hubs for API management in cities.

API tool can be opted for to achieve the best API gateway. In contrast, Microsoft Azure can be deployed to streamline how city developers develop, analyze, manage, and extend digital services in enabling a modern digital eco-system. Additionally, Microsoft Azure can be used to quickly create sophisticated APIs and services for applications and can be customized and simplified to deliver and manage APIs services across smart cities. Microsoft Azure analyzes API digital performance with metrics that provide visibility. Lastly, Microsoft Azure can be extended to develop a digital ecosystem to increase innovation and value of digital services in making cities smarter.

Discussion

The seamless exchange of data across several devices and digital systems in realizing a smart city eco-system is no longer far away (Costin and Eastman, 2019). Previous review studies (See Table 4) provided insight into the research trend of interoperability. However, the reviewed studies neglected to explore seamless interoperability of digital systems with regard to deployment of API in smart cities. Therefore, in this study an SLR is carried out for interoperability studies related to smart cities, attempting to provide a comprehensive description of the role of API in addressing service interoperability. This study provides a synopsis of how API can be employed to enable seamless service interoperability in making cities smarter. Findings from this study are consistent

Table 6. Comparison of API management tools

API Tools	Provides Gateway	Publishing Tools	Developer Portal or API store	Reporting and Analytics	Monetization	Facilitates Governance	Opensource (Free)
Apigee	y	y	y	y	y	y	n
3scale	n	y	y	y	y	y	y
IBM API Tool	n	y	y	y	y	y	n
Akana	n	y	y	y	n	y	n
Kong API Tool	n	y	y	y	n	y	y
Dell Boomi	n	n	y	y	n	n	n
Mashery	n	y	y	y	y	y	n
Automate	y	n	y	y	y	n	n
MuleSoft	y	y	y	y	n	y	n
Microsoft Azure	y	y	y	y	y	y	n
Oracle SOA	n	n	y	y	n	y	n
Postman	n	y	y	y	n	n	n
Axway	n	y	y	y	n	y	n
WSO2	n	y	y	y	y	y	y
Cloud Elements	n	y	y	y	n	n	n

with results from prior studies (Bhatt et al., 2017; Karpenko et al., 2018), which suggests that API plays an important role in providing access to open data and facilitates integration of systems in urban space.

Moreover, findings from this study indicate that API aids in developing distributed services that help achieve smart city ecosystem as mentioned by Ahlgren et al. (2016). Findings from this study are in line with results from Noura et al. (2019), which revealed that API can enable seamless interoperable system integration in smart cities. Similar to results from the literature (Gessa and Sancha, 2019; Tomor et al., 2019; Yousefi and Dadashpoor, 2019), this study also sought to contribute to the literature on sustainable urban technology by giving guidance for future research on service interoperability by showing how available closed data could be made accessible for city developers. In addition, findings from this study identify the categories of interoperability, specifying available API management tools that can be utilized to improve service interoperability in making cities smarter were described analogous to prior studies (softwaretestinghelp.com, 2019; Kerner, 2019).

To conclude, the findings of this study provide insight into the current trend of interoperability research in smart cities and offers valuable reference as suggested by Costin and Eastman (2019) for future studies in service interoperability in making urban environment smarter. Additionally, this study designs a use scenario that illustrates how APIs supports seamless interoperability across digital systems in smart cities in a developed architecture as seen in Figure 7. This suggests that APIs can be employed to improve current services provided to citizens by enabling seamless services in urban environment.

Conclusion

Smart cities comprise different systems that generate data. However, the data are stuck in vertically closed applications with limited interoperability between the digital systems.

This hinders seamless services that limit the connection between heterogeneous systems. This issue is especially important since smart cities comprise many diverse service providers that must collaborate with each other to provide quality services to citizens. Thus, the seamless data exchanges between various systems are important to attain a sustainable urban system. But interoperability is one of the major issues in realizing the vision of making cities smarter, where interoperability enables vendors and city developers to interact and produce innovative services for the city and beyond.

Therefore, the purpose of this research was to conduct a review that focuses on the interoperability issues in smart cities. Therefore, API is suggested to provide a solution to city developers to address technical requirements and business needs for interoperable digital systems ultimately providing improved services to citizens and stakeholders. API provides access to existing data silos in the city to efficiently manage the city and improve citizens' awareness as seen in the case scenario presented in [Figure 7](#). As a limitation, this study only reported on the role of API for seamless interoperability of digital systems and was restricted to secondary data from the literatures. In that, API was not designed, deployed, or published. Respectively, ongoing research currently focuses on the creation and deployment of open APIs to provide value added services for smart mobility, energy, and air quality in making cities smarter.

Notes on contributor

Bokolo Anthony Jnr. is currently a senior researcher in the Department of Applied Data Science, Institute for Energy Technology (IFE), Halden, Norway. He is also an associate professor in the Department of Computer Science and Communication, Østfold University College, Norway.

Acknowledgement

Open access funding provided by Institute for Energy Technology (IFE), Norway.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

References

- R. A. Abdelouahid, L. Chhiba, A. Marzak, A. Mamouni, and N. Sael, "IoT Interoperability Architectures: Comparative Study," *First International Conference on Real Time Intelligent Systems* (2017) 209–215.
- B. Ahlgren, M. Hidell, and E. C. H. Ngai, "Internet of Things for Smart Cities: Interoperability and Open Data," *IEEE Internet Computing* 20:6 (2016) 52–56.
- D. Andročec, "Overcoming Service-Level Interoperability Challenges of the IoT," *Connected Environments for the Internet of Things* (Springer, Cham, 2017) 3–101.
- B. Anthony Jnr, "Smart City Data Architecture for Energy Prosumption in Municipalities: Concepts, Requirements, and Future Directions," *International Journal of Green Energy* 17:13 (2020a) 827–845.
- B. Anthony Jnr, "Applying Enterprise Architecture for Digital Transformation of Electro Mobility Towards Sustainable Transportation," *In Proceedings of the 2020 on Computers and People Research Conference* (2020b) 38–46.

- B. Anthony Jnr, "Managing Digital Transformation of Smart Cities Through Enterprise Architecture—A Review and Research Agenda," *Enterprise Information Systems* 15:3 (2021a) 299–331.
- B. Anthony Jnr, "Exploring Data Driven Initiatives for Smart City Development: Empirical Evidence from Techno-Stakeholders' Perspective," *Urban Research and Practice* (2021b) 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17535069.2020.1869816>.
- B. Anthony Jnr, "A Case-Based Reasoning Recommender System for Sustainable Smart City Development," *AI and SOCIETY* 36:1 (2021c) 159–183.
- B. Anthony Jnr, "Integrating Electric Vehicles to Achieve Sustainable Energy as a Service Business Model in Smart Cities," *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities* 3 (2021d) 685716.
- B. Anthony Jnr, S. Abbas Petersen, D. Ahlers, and J. Krogstie, "API Deployment for Big Data Management Towards Sustainable Energy Prosumption in Smart Cities—A Layered Architecture Perspective," *International Journal of Sustainable Energy* 39 (2020a) 263–289.
- B. Anthony Jnr, S. A. Petersen, D. Ahlers, and J. Krogstie, "Big Data Driven Multi-Tier Architecture for Electric Mobility as a Service In Smart Cities: A Design Science Approach," *International Journal of Energy Sector Management* 14 (2020b) 1023–1047. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJESM-08-2019-0001>.
- B. Anthony, S. A. Petersen, D. Ahlers, J. Krogstie, and K. Livik "Big Data-Oriented Energy Prosumption Service in Smart Community Districts: A Multi-Case Study Perspective," *Energy Informatics* 2 (2019) 1–26.
- B. Anthony, S. A. Petersen, and M. Helfert, "Digital Transformation of Virtual Enterprises For Providing Collaborative Services in Smart Cities," in *Boosting Collaborative Networks 4.0: 21st IFIP WG 5.5 Working Conference on Virtual Enterprises, PRO-VE 2020, Valencia, Spain, November 23–25, 2020, Proceedings* 21, pp. 249–260. Springer International Publishing, 2020.
- B. Anthony Jnr, S. A. Petersen, M. Helfert, and H. Guo, "Digital Transformation with Enterprise Architecture for Smarter Cities: A Qualitative Research Approach," *Digital Policy, Regulation and Governance* (2021a). <https://doi.org/10.1108/DPRG-04-2020-0044>.
- B. Anthony Jnr, S. A. Petersen, M. Helfert, D. Ahlers, and J. Krogstie, "Modeling Pervasive Platforms and Digital Services for Smart Urban Transformation Using an Enterprise Architecture Framework," *Information Technology and People* 34 (2021b) 1285–1312. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITP-07-2020-0511>.
- S. A. Barbosa, G. Leite, A. S. Oliveira, T. O. de Jesus, D. D. de Macedo, and R. P. do Nascimento, "An Architecture Proposal for The Creation of a Database to Open Data Related to ITS in Smart Cities," *8th Euro American Conference on Telematics and Information Systems* (2016) 1–7.
- L. Bedogni, L. Bononi, M. Di Felice, A. D'Elia, R. Mock, F. Montori, ... and F. Vergari, "An Interoperable Architecture for Mobile Smart Services over the Internet of Energy," *14th International Symposium on A World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks* (2013) 1–6.
- A. J. Berre, B. Elvesæter, N. Figay, C. Guglielmina, S. G. Johnsen, D. Karlsen, ... and S. Lippe, "The ATHENA Interoperability Framework," *Enterprise interoperability II* (Springer London, 2007) 569–580.
- V. Bhatt, A. Brutti, M. Burns, and A. Frascella, "An Approach to Provide Shared Architectural Principles for Interoperable Smart Cities," *International Conference on Computational Science and its Applications* (2017) 415–426.
- O. Borgogno, and G. Colangelo, "Data Sharing and Interoperability: Fostering Innovation and Competition Through APIs," *Computer Law and Security Review* 35:5 (2019) 1–17.
- A. Bröring, S. Schmid, C. K. Schindhelm, A. Khelil, S. Käbisch, D. Kramer, ... and E. Teniente, "Enabling IoT Ecosystems Through Platform Interoperability," *IEEE software* 34 (2017) 54–61.
- F. G. Brundu, E. Patti, A. Osello, M. Del Giudice, N. Rapetti, A. Krylovskiy, ... and A. Acquaviva, "IoT Software Infrastructure for Energy Management and Simulation in Smart Cities," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, 13 (2016) 832–840.
- A. Brutti, P. De Sabbata, A. Frascella, N. Gessa, R. Ianniello, C. Novelli, ... and G. Ponti, "Smart City Platform Specification: A Modular Approach to Achieve Interoperability in Smart

- Cities,” *The Internet of Things for Smart Urban Ecosystems* (2019) 25–50. (Springer: New York, 2029)
- R. Camagni, R. Capello, and A. Caragliu, “Measuring the Impact of Legal and Administrative International Barriers on Regional Growth,” *Regional Science Policy and Practice* 11 (2019) 345–366.
- J. Cecilio, F., Caldeira and C. Wanzeller, “CityMii-An Integration and Interoperable Middleware to Manage a Smart City,” *Procedia Computer Science* 130 (2018) 416–423.
- K. Chaturvedi, and T. H. Kolbe, “InterSensor Service: Establishing Interoperability Over Heterogeneous Sensor Observations and Platforms for Smart Cities,” *International Smart Cities Conference* (2018) 1–8.
- M. Choi, Y. S. Jeong, and J. H. Park, “Improving Performance Through Rest Open API Grouping for Wireless Sensor Network,” *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks* 9 (2013) 1–13. 958241.
- A. Costin, and C. Eastman, “Need for Interoperability to Enable Seamless Information Exchanges in Smart and Sustainable Urban Systems,” *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering* 33 (2019) 04019008. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CP.1943-5487.0000824](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CP.1943-5487.0000824)
- P. Desai, A. Sheth, and P. Anantharam, “Semantic Gateway as a Service Architecture for IoT Interoperability,” *International Conference on Mobile Services* (2015) 313–319.
- D. Dhungana, G. Engelbrecht, J. X. Parreira, A. Schuster, and D. Valerio, “Aspern smart ICT: Data Analytics and Privacy Challenges in a Smart City,” *2nd World Forum on Internet of Things* (2015) 447–452.
- B. Di Martino, M. Rak, M. Ficco, A. Esposito, S. A. Maisto, and S. Nacchia, “Internet of Things Reference Architectures, Security and Interoperability: A Survey,” *Internet of Things* 1 (2018) 99–112.
- EC-European Commission, “New European Interoperability Framework. Promoting Seamless Services and Data Flows for European Public Administrations,” (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2017).
- R. T. Fielding, and R. N. Taylor, “*Architectural Styles and the Design of Network-Based Software Architectures*,” Doctoral dissertation: University of California, Irvine 7 (2000).
- G. Fortino, C. Savaglio, C. E. Palau, J. S. de Puga, M. Ganzha, M. Paprzycki, ... and M. Llop, “Towards Multi-Layer Interoperability of Heterogeneous IoT Platforms: The INTER-IoT Approach,” *Integration, Interconnection, and Interoperability of IoT Systems* (2018) 199–232.
- A. Gessa, and P. Sancha, “Environmental Open Data in Urban Platforms: An Approach to the Big Data Life Cycle,” *Journal of Urban Technology* 27:1 (2019) 1–19.
- A. Gyrard, and M. Serrano, “Connected Smart Cities: Interoperability with Seg 3.0 for the Internet of Things,” *30th International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications Workshops* (2016) 796–802.
- K. Holley, S. Antoun, A. Arsanjani, W. A. Brown, C. Cozzi, J. F. Costas, ... and J. Laredo, “The Power of the API Economy—Stimulate Innovation, Increase Productivity, Develop New Channels, and Reach New Markets,” *IBM Corporate* (2014).
- IEEE, “IEEE Standard Glossary of Software Engineering Terminology,” *IEEE Std 610.12-1990* (1990) 1–84.
- A. Karpenko, T. Kinnunen, M. Madhikermi, J. Robert, K. Främling, B. Dave, and A. Nurminen, “Data Exchange Interoperability in IoT Ecosystem for Smart Parking and EV Charging,” *Sensors* 18 (2018) 4404. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s18124404>
- S. M. Kerner, Top 10 API Management Tools, published by *datamation* (2019) <https://www.datamation.com/applications/top-api-management-tools.html> Accessed 12-10-2023.
- B. Kitchenham, O. P. Brereton, D. Budgen, M. Turner, J. Bailey, and S. Linkman, “Systematic Literature Reviews in Software Engineering—A Systematic Literature Review,” *Information and Software Technology* 51 (2009) 7–15.
- E. Kovacs, M. Bauer, J. Kim, J. Yun, F. Le Gall, and M. Zhao, “Standards-based Worldwide Semantic Interoperability for IoT,” *IEEE Communications Magazine* 54 (2016) 40–46.
- A. Lagendijk, and A. Lorentzen, “Proximity, Knowledge and Innovation in Peripheral Regions. On the Intersection Between Geographical and Organizational Proximity,” *European Planning Studies*, 15 (2007) 457–466.

- N. Loutas, E. Kamateri, and K. Tarabanis, “Cloud4SOA, Cloud Semantic Interoperability Framework” (2011). Deliverable D1.
- D. Manzaroli, L. Roffia, T. S. Cinotti, E. Ovaska, P. Azzoni, V. Nannini, and S. Mattarozzi, “Smart-M3 and OSGi: The Interoperability Platform,” *The IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications* (2010) 1053–1058.
- H. McGrath, M. Kotsollaris, E. Stefanakis, and M. Nastev, “Flood Damage Calculations via a RESTful API,” *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 35 (2019) 101071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2019.101071>
- P. Nesi, C. Badii, P. Bellini, D. Cenni, G. Martelli, and M. Paolucci, “Km4City Smart City API: an Integrated Support for Mobility Services,” *IEEE International Conference on Smart Computing* (2016) 1–8.
- H. M. Nguyen, J. Byun, K. Kwon, J. Han, W. Yoon, N. Lee, ... and D. Kim, “Oliot-OpenCity: Open Standard Interoperable Smart City Platform,” *International Smart Cities Conference* (2018) 1–8.
- M. Noura, M. Atiquzzaman, and M. Gaedke, “Interoperability in Internet Of Things: Taxonomies and Open Challenges,” *Mobile Networks and Applications* 24 (2019) 796–809.
- M. Pradhan, N. Suri, C. Fuchs, T. H. Bloebaum, and M. Marks, “Toward an Architecture and Data Model to Enable Interoperability Between Federated Mission Networks and IoT-enabled Smart City Environments,” *IEEE Communications Magazine* 56 (2018) 163–169.
- C. Raetzsch, G. Pereira, L. S. Vestergaard, and M. Brynskov, “Weaving seams with data: Conceptualizing City APIs as elements of infrastructures,” *Big Data and Society* 6 (2019) 1–14. 2053951719827619.
- A. Rech, M. Pistauer, and C. Steger, “Increasing Interoperability Between Heterogeneous Smart City Applications,” *International Conference on Internet and Distributed Computing Systems* 11226 (2018) 64–74.
- J. Robert, S. Kubler, N. Kolbe, A. Cerioni, E. Gastaud, and K. Främling, “Open IoT Ecosystem for Enhanced Interoperability in Smart Cities—Example of Métropole de Lyon,” *Sensors* 17 (2017) 2849.
- J. M. Schleicher, M. Vögler, C. Inzinger, and S. Dustdar, “Modeling and Management of Usage-Aware Distributed Datasets for Global Smart City Application Ecosystems,” *PeerJ Computer Science* 3 (2017) e115. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.115>
- softwaretestinghelp.com, “Top 10 Best API management tools with feature comparison,” published by *softwaretestinghelp* (2019) <https://www.softwaretestinghelp.com/api-management-tools/> Accessed 12-10-2023.
- Z. Tomor, A. Meijer, A. Michels, and S. Geertman, “Smart Governance for Sustainable Cities: Findings from a Systematic Literature Review,” *Journal of Urban Technology* 26 (2019) 3–27.
- H. Yliopisto, “Department of Computer Science, F. Eliassen, and J. Veijalainen, A Functional Approach to Information System Interoperability,” (1988). <https://searchworks.stanford.edu/view/4615118>
- Z. Yousefi, and H. Dadashpoor, “How Do ICTs Affect Urban Spatial Structure? A Systematic Literature Review,” *Journal of Urban Technology* 27:1 (2019) 1–19.
- A. Zabasta, N. Kunicina, K. Kondratjevs, A. Patlins, L. Ribickis, and J. Delsing, MQTT Service Broker for Enabling the Interoperability of Smart City Systems. *Energy and Sustainability for Small Developing Economies* (2018) 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.03.245>
- M. Zuccalà, and E. S. Verga, “Enabling Energy Smart Cities Through Urban Sharing Ecosystems,” *Energy Procedia* 111 (2017) 826–835.